

References

1. C. SINGH and C. N. KACHRU, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1971, 34, 137.
2. C. SINGH and C. N. KACHRU, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1971, 34, 272.
3. C. N. KACHRU and B. PATHAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 611, 768.
4. B. S. KAUSHIVA, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1957, 16C, 224.

Partial Molal Volume of Ions in N-Methyl Acetamide Solutions

RAM GOPAL* and MOHD. ASLAM SIDDIQI

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow.

Manuscript received 16 November 1977, revised 10 April 1978
accepted 14 September 1978

THE ionic volume of univalent ions in water¹, formamide^{2,3}, N-methylpropionamide^{4,5}, methanol⁴, ethanol⁶, sea water⁷, dimethyl formamide⁸, ethylene glycol and formic acid⁹ are now available in the literature and the data have been employed by several workers to study interactions in solutions. Similar data in N-methylacetamide (NMA) are lacking although the apparent molal volumes of a number of uni-univalent electrolytes were reported from this laboratory¹⁰ some years ago. From the electrolyte limiting apparent molal volume data already reported¹⁰, apparent (partial) ionic volumes for common ions have been evaluated and these have been used to investigate the nature of ion-NMA interaction in solution.

Procedure: For the sake of convenience, the limiting apparent molal volume ϕ° ($\equiv \bar{V}^\circ$) values for different salts in NMA at 35° are reproduced¹⁰ in Table 1.

TABLE 1—LIMITING PARTIAL MOLAL VOLUMES $\bar{V}^\circ$ ($= \phi^\circ$) OF SOME SALTS IN NMA AT 35°C

Salt	LiCl	NaCl	NaBr	NaI	NaNO ₃	KBr	KI	KNO ₃	NH ₄ Cl	NH ₄ Br	NH ₄ I	NH ₄ NO ₃
$\bar{V}^\circ$ {cm ³ mol ⁻¹ }	20.5	26.0	32.6	42.0	35.0	40.2	45.9	42.8	35.5	44.7	51.7	47.2

The additivity law has been found to hold good for $\bar{V}^\circ$ values of electrolytes in N-methylacetamide as in other solvents^{1,3,4} and the $\bar{V}^\circ$ of salts have been divided into ionic contribution, using the method of Mukerjee¹ which assumes that for spherical, large alkali metal and halide ions, the partial molal volumes should be a smooth monotonic function of the crystallographic radius (r), quite independent of the sign of the charge. The partial molal volumes of various ions at infinite dilution are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THE $\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)}$ OF SOME MONOVALENT IONS IN NMA AT 35°C

Ion	Crystal radius ^a (in Å°)	$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)}$ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\frac{\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)}r}{z^2}$	$\frac{r^4}{z^2}$
Na ⁺	0.95	3.4	3.0	0.81
K ⁺	1.33	8.8	11.7	3.13
NH ₄ ⁺	1.60	15.4	24.6	6.55
Cl ⁻	1.81	22.4	40.5	10.73
Br ⁻	1.95	28.2	55.0	14.47
I ⁻	2.16	38.6	83.4	21.76
NO ₃ ⁻	2.03	31.9	64.8	16.98

^a—Pauling radii, Pauling, L. "The nature of the Chemical Bond", 3rd. Ed. Cornell University Press, Ithaca, N.Y. 1940.

Discussion

The limiting partial molal volume of an ion may be assumed to be the sum of two major contributions², namely, the geometric part and the electrostriction part and can be written as

$$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)} = \bar{V}^\circ_{(geom.)} + \bar{V}^\circ_{(elst.)} \quad (i)$$

where $\bar{V}^\circ_{(geom.)}$ takes into account the intrinsic volume of the ions plus the void space effects created on introducing the ions in the solvent and $\bar{V}^\circ_{(elst.)}$, the contribution of electrostriction due to electrostatic ion-solvent dipole interaction.

A number of relations have been proposed connecting these two effects with the radius of the ion^{11,12} these are

$$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)} = Ar^3 - \frac{Bz^2}{r} \quad (ii)$$

$$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)} = 2.52r^3 + (A-2.52)r^3 - \frac{Bz^2}{r} \quad (iii)$$

and
$$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)} = 2.52r^3 + A^1r^3 - \frac{B^1z^2}{r} \quad (iv)$$

The simple equations (ii) and (iii) have been used to separate the geometric part and the electrostriction part of the ionic volume.

Equation (ii) may be rearranged in a more useful form,

$$\frac{\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{ion})r}{z^2} = A \frac{r^4}{z^2} - B \quad (v)$$

in order to determine the coefficients A and B, the values of $\frac{\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{ion})r}{z^2}$ and $\frac{r^4}{z^2}$ for different ions are given in columns 4 & 5 of Table 2. The plot of $\frac{\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{ion})r}{z^2}$ vs $\frac{r^4}{z^2}$ is shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1 : Plot of $\frac{\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{ion})r}{z^2}$ versus $\frac{r^4}{z^2}$

TABLE 3—CONSTANTS 'A' AND 'B' OF EQ. (I) IN SOME SOLVENTS

Solvent	Dielectric constant	Temp. °C	Constant 'A' (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ A ⁰⁻²)	Constant 'B' (cm ³ mol ⁻¹ A ⁰)
Ethanol ^a	24.3 ^c	25	3.3	12.0
Methanol ^b	31.5 ^d	25	3.5	16.0
Water ^b	78.5 ^a	25	4.5	8.0
Formamide ^c	108.7 ^e	25	4.3	2.5
NMP ^b	163.1 ^e	25	4.0	3.0
NMA	171.7 ^e	35	3.9	1.5

^a values taken from reference (8)

^b " " " (4)

^c " " " (9)

^d " " " (13)

^e " " " (14)

From the slope and intercept of the linear curve, the constants 'A' and 'B' have been evaluated as 3.9 and 1.5 respectively. The value of constants 'A' and 'B' for various hydrogen bonded solvents are summarised in Table 3.

The geometric part of the partial molal volume has further been divided into the intrinsic size of the ion $\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{ion})$ and the void space effect $\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{disord.})$ using equation (iii). Table 4 gives the $\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{disord.})$ calculated as above [i.e. $\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{disord.}) = (A-2.52)r^3$] for various ions in NMA and compared with those in other solvents.

TABLE 4—DISORDERED PARTIAL MOLAL VOLUMES $\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{disord.})$, FOR SOME UNIVALENT IONS IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS.

Solvent	$\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{disord.}) = (A-2.52)r^3$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹ for ions				
	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Cl ⁻	Br ⁻	I ⁻
Ethanol ^a	0.7	1.9	4.7	5.9	8.1
Methanol ^a	0.9	2.4	5.9	7.4	10.1
Water ^a	1.7	4.7	11.9	14.8	20.2
Formamide ^a	1.5	4.2	10.7	13.3	18.1
NMP ^a	1.3	3.5	8.9	11.1	15.1
NMA	1.2	3.2	8.2	10.2	13.9

^a values at 25°C taken from reference (9).

It may be noted from Table 3 that the value of 'A' is always larger than the theoretical value (2.52) calculated by assuming that the ion is a perfect hard sphere. The increase in the intrinsic volume of an ion in NMA is about 57% as compared to crystal volume. The increase in other solvents is 77% in water¹, 59% in NMP^{4,5}, 32% in methanol⁴ and 29% in ethanol⁸. This apparent increase in the intrinsic volume may be attributed to void space packing effect^{15,16,17} and disorder region surrounding the ion⁴. Thus the intrinsic volume of an ion in solution should be directly related to the structure of the solvent. It is largest (constant 'A' = 4.5) in the highly ordered solvent like water^{18,19} due to its ability to form three dimensional hydrogen bonds. Criss and coworkers²⁰ similarly relate the partial molal entropy of ions in various solvents to the structure of the solvent.

A comparison of constant 'B' of equation (ii) and the electrostriction caused by various ions in NMA is not possible since the calculation of 'B' theoretically²¹ from the relation

$$\bar{V}^{\circ}(\text{elect.}) = -\frac{Nc^2z^2}{2Dr} \left(\frac{d \ln D}{dp} \right) = -B \frac{z^2}{r} \quad (vi)$$

would require the pressure dependence of the dielectric constant of the solvent which is not available for NMA. However, a comparison of 'B' in different solvents indicates that 'B' is, in general, inversely proportional

to the dielectric constant, D , of the solvent^{4,8,9}. Qualitatively, it justifies the usual notion that the electrostriction effect or the ion-dipole interaction gets weaker, the larger the dielectric constant of the medium. Since one is dealing with the infinite dilution while considering $\bar{V}_{i,0}^{\circ}$ values, the bulk dielectric constant of the medium will be effective and the results justify the theoretical expectation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Chemistry Dept., Lucknow University, Lucknow, for laboratory facilities. One of us (M.A.S.) is also grateful to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. P. MUKHERJEE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 740.
2. R. GOPAL and R. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 2704.
3. R. GOPAL and R. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 99.
4. F. J. MILLERO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 2417.
5. F. J. MILLERO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, 72, 3209.
6. F. KAWAIZUMI and R. ZANA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, 78, 627.
7. F. J. MILLERO, *Limnol. Oceanogr.*, 1969, 14, 376.
8. F. KAWAIZUMI and R. ZANA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, 78, 1099.
9. U. SEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, 81, 35.
10. R. GOPAL, M. A. SIDDIQI and K. SINGH, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1971, 75, 7.
11. L. G. HEPLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, 61, 1426.
12. F. J. MILLERO, "Water and Aqueous solutions". R. A. HORNE, Ed., Wiley, New York, N. Y. 1972.
13. H. S. HVRNED and B. B. OWEN, "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic solutions", ACS Monograph, Reinhold Publishing Corp., N. Y. 1958.
14. S. J. BASS, W. I. NATHAN, R. M. MEIGHAN and R. H. COLE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 509.
15. B. E. CONWAY, R. E. VERRAL and J. F. DESNOYERS, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1965, 230, 157.
16. E. GLUECKAUF, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, 61, 914.
17. S. W. BENSON and C. S. COPELAND, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 1194.
18. H. S. FRANK and M. W. EVANS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, 13, 507.
19. H. S. FRANK and W. Y. WEN, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 133.
20. C. CRISS, R. P. HELD and E. LUKSHA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, 72, 2970.
21. P. DRUDE and W. NERNST, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1894, 15, 79.